

Non-Destructive inspection solutions in the EU industrial sector for sustainable manufacturing

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Abstract The development of NDI solutions is required to advance from a scenario where the visual and dimensional inspection is performed by operators, in which monitoring is a slow process and the data collaboration is scarce; to a scenario where using visual inspection tools, digital platforms, data processing, monitoring, and reacting are agile and collaborative processes. Deploying at factory shopfloor intelligent digital capabilities to boost financial and sustainability performance.

Keywords: production; sustainability; quality inspection; control.

1 Introduction

The increasing emphasis on developing the EU industrial sector based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) requires governments and private companies to reduce resource consumption in the entire industrial ecosystem (Affairs, 2019). To address these new challenges, the industry should increase its efforts in developing and integrating solutions based on Zero Defects and Zero Waste (ZDZW). The ZDZW strategy aims at the early detection of anomalies and faults using inspection equipment and classifying them through the employment of artificial intelligence algorithms, avoiding their propagation to the next stages of production. The goal of the ZDM strategy is that all of the products are inspected with non-destructive methods, therefore no defective product reaches the customer and no excessive waste is generated in the quality control inspection (Caiazzo et al., 2022).

The quality assurance of parts has an important effect on the product service life since the defects (cracks, scratches, inclusions, etc.) are the major factors for product performance (Lario et al., 2023). Therefore, the quality of the final products must be tested in several process steps, and before it leaves the factory to ensure their reliability. The End-Of-Line (EOL) quality inspection usually leads to a time-

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consuming rework stage and decreases the part profit margin since the defective parts are detected when all the manufacturing steps have been completed. Another disadvantage of destructive evaluation is labour intensive, time-consuming, and expensive. These techniques are considered offline and cannot send direct feedback to the manufacturing process, increasing the material, energy consumption, and percentage of scrapped parts.

Current non-destructive inspection technologies are applied in critical applications (e.g. aerospace, pressure vessels, energy production) to continuously monitor high-risk structures or infrastructures (Avdelidis et al., 2006; Shaloo et al., 2022). The NDIT, together with AI algorithms and Digital Twin presents the ability to detect defects or lack of control on a real-time basis, and these solutions present an advantage for advance for sustainable production since improve the decision-making process and reduce the downstream quality inspection (Mourtzis et al., 2021). Early defect detection and classification through AI algorithms avoid their propagation downstream to other production stages, which increases production costs (Ding et al., 2020).

The aim of this article is, therefore, to present several non-destructive inspection technologies, together with AI algorithms for defect detection and digital twin for process control, required for the development of next-generation Zero-Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) solutions.

2 Conventional Quality Control

In conventional quality assurance policies, the products are inspected at the end of the process (EOP) by sampling or at the end of the line (EOL) (Chrysler Corporation et al., 1994; Taylor, 2017). If the inspection batch is rejected can end in a high amount of scrap product. In most cases, quality control is performed by destructive testing (such as flexural strength or axial compression test) or contact methods (such as ultrasonic, callipers or micrometre), which reduces productivity and increases costs.

Fig. 1 Conventional quality control flow diagram.

Conventional quality assurance policies are based on offline inspection or testing according to a preestablished sampling plan (Fig. 1), where an operator performs a manual inspection using a measurement tool or instruments (calliper, micrometres, or gages). Another methodology is the part inspection employing Visual Inspection methodologies. The most basic one is where the inspector's observations result in a quantitative assessment of the part quality. Typically, naked eye inspections can identify features on the order of $1\mu\text{m}$ by touch and sight, simple manipulations, and light reflection on the surface object (Sharratt, 2015). The human visual inspection approach presents two main disadvantages, the quality inspection is performed offline with the consequent time delay, and it is often too late when defects are detected, which may end in high material and resource wastage, negatively impacting the production sustainability. This inspection method is composed of tedious repetitive tasks, and after several hours the human vision is subjected to ocular fatigue.

3 Advantages Non-Destructive inspection technologies

In the past decade, research on non-destructive technologies using camera vision, IR thermography, OCT, acoustic emission, and AE has gained industry attention because they are cost-effective for quality control in real-time the manufacturing process (Psarommatis et al., 2022). The utilization of non-destructive techniques presents the main advantage that allows the examination of the components or parts without destroying them or changing their properties. The main bottleneck for the integration of NDI is the return on investment (ROI), since these types of equipment or solutions present a high level of complexity the range of ROI can range from 12 – 48 months. Non-destructive inspection allows to extract features of interest from a digital image or sensors that can be processed through algorithms and mathematical models for defect detection and dimensional control (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 A layered-level semantic platform for the implementation of automatic NDI solutions.

The manufacturing process requires the integration of Key Inspection Solutions (KIS) to assure the production of higher-quality products, while simultaneously reducing energy and resource consumption and increasing the sustainability of the entire industrial ecosystem. The transversal integration of KIS (e.g., NDIT, AI, Digital Twin) in the production lines aims to reduce the scrap rate, increase productivity, improve energy efficiency and material consumption. The development and implementation of quality inspection strategies based on NDIT must combine different areas of expertise, such as materials science, engineering, information systems, and data analytics (Ding et al., 2020; Mourtzis et al., 2021; Psarommatis et al., 2022; Wang, 2013). The next generations of in-process inspection solutions for the industrial sector will be based on some of these technologies, such as Electro Magnetic Acoustic Transducer (EMAT), Acoustic emissions (AE), or Mid Infrared Optical Coherence Tomography (MIR-OCT). The implementation of KIS will pursue the automatic quality control inspection base in a more effective and reliable inspection. These solutions can be integrated into AM machines or automated production lines, and the defective pieces can be automatically rejected, avoiding the deployment in the downstream process (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 In-process ZDZW quality control flow diagram.

The present ZDZW strategies will be validated in six industrial sectors (automotive industry, consumer goods, food and drink, energy production, metal, and medical) developing universal inspection solutions required for improving the manufacturing sustainability of the EU industry.

4 NDIT improvement in sustainability

Some of the causes that make the industrial process inefficient and with poor sustainability are low process repeatability, which makes the process expensive waste due to high scrap rate or trial-and-error nature. Or the high inspection cost

and characterization of parts by human intervention or destructive testing. An efficient quality inspection allows a higher level of product efficiency, less material waste, and less energy consumption, which leads to more sustainable manufacturing. The implementation of zero-defect manufacturing strategies (detection/ prediction /prevention /repair) improves the quality by “making it right the first time” rather than trying to mitigate a problem at a later stage. The application of NDIT solutions will contribute to preventing the generation of defects and consequently increase process efficiency and sustainability (Ed & Hutchison, 2019). The integration of current quality assurance capabilities will ensure in-line quality inspections, defect detection, and improvement of production efficiency and profitability (Psarommatis & Bravos, 2023).

5 Conclusions

The implementation of inspection solutions based on NDIT, AI algorithms, and DTs, in the manufacturing process offers a new path for in-line or in-process defect detection and grant propagation avoidance on downstream process steps, in contrast to conventional end-of-line sampling inspection solutions, in order to reduce resource consumption and improve production margin profit. The integration of KIS enables the possibility of downstream compensation, rework, or scrap.

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References

Affairs, U. N. D. of E. and S. (2019). The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2019. *United Nations Publication Issued by the Department of Economic and Social Affairs*, 64. <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2022/%0Ahttps://www.un-ilibrary.org/content/books/9789210018098%0Ahttps://www.un-ilibrary.org/content/books/9789210478878>

- Avdelidis, N. P., Almond, D. P., Dobbinson, A., & Hawtin, B. C. (2006). Pulsed thermography : philosophy , qualitative quantitative analysis on aircraft materials & applications. In *Proceedings of Vth International Workshop, Advances in Signal Processing for Non Destructive Evaluation of Materials*.
- Caiazzo, B., Di Nardo, M., Murino, T., Petrillo, A., Piccirillo, G., & Santini, S. (2022). Towards Zero Defect Manufacturing paradigm: A review of the state-of-the-art methods and open challenges. In *Computers in Industry*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2021.103548>
- Chrysler Corporation, Ford Motor Company, & General Motors Corporation. (1994). Advanced product quality planning (APQP) and control plan. Retrieved October, June 1994, 128.
- Ding, H., Gao, R. X., Isaksson, A. J., Landers, R. G., Parisini, T., & Yuan, Y. (2020). State of AI-Based Monitoring in Smart Manufacturing and Introduction to Focused Section. *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, 25(5), 2143–2154. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMECH.2020.3022983>
- Ed, M. K., & Hutchison, D. (2019). *Human-Computer Interaction*.
- Femenia, J. L. (2023). *Powder Metallurgy : A New Path for Advanced Titanium Alloys in the EU Medical Device Supply Chain*. 1–16.
- Mourtzis, D., Angelopoulos, J., & Panopoulos, N. (2021). Equipment Design Optimization Based on Digital Twin under the Framework of Zero-Defect Manufacturing. *Procedia Computer Science*, 180(2019), 525–533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.01.271>
- Psarommatis, F., & Bravos, G. (2023). ScienceDirect A holistic approach for achieving Sustainable manufacturing using Zero Defect Manufacturing : a conceptual Framework. *Procedia CIRP*, 107(March), 107–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2022.04.018>
- Psarommatis, F., Sousa, J., Mendonça, J. P., & Kiritsis, D. (2022). Zero-defect manufacturing the approach for higher manufacturing sustainability in the era of industry 4.0: a position paper. *International Journal of Production Research*, 60(1), 73–91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2021.1987551>
- Shaloo, M., Schnall, M., Klein, T., Huber, N., & Reiting, B. (2022). A Review of Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) Techniques for Defect Detection: Application to Fusion Welding and Future Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing Processes. *Materials*, 15(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15103697>
- Sharratt, B. M. (2015). Non-Destructive Techniques and Technologies for Qualification of Additive Manufactured Parts and Processes: A Literature Review. *Department of National Defence of Canada*, 55(March), 91–127.
- Taylor, W. A. (2017). *Statistical Procedures for the Medical Device Industry*. Taylor Enterprises, Incorporated. <https://books.google.es/books?id=F50etAEA-CAAJ>
- Wang, K. S. (2013). Towards zero-defect manufacturing (ZDM)-a data mining approach. *Advances in Manufacturing*, 1(1), 62–74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40436-013-0010-9>